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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MUNDARIJA

Katta guruh tarbiyalanuvchilarida kasb haqidagi dastlabki tasavvurlarni shakllantirish metodikasini innovatsion ekotizim sharoitida takomillashtirish	18
Uralova Fotima Baxtiyor qizi	
Malakali sportchilarning kommunikativ qobiliyatlarini takomillashtirishda sotsiologik yondashuv (gandbolchilar misolida).....	23
G. A. Valiyeva	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida motor alaiyali bolalarni ruhiy va nutqiy rivojlantirish usullari	27
Suyunova Surayyo Ulash qizi	
Sog'lom bola ekotizimining asoslari: ovqatlanish, immunitet va rivojlanish	31
Israilova Xusnida Adilovna	
Mobil ilovalar yordamida mustaqil o'qishni rivojlantirish	37
Raximova Feruza Najmiddinovna	
Biologiya darslarida muammoli ta'lim texnologiyasini qo'llash orqali mantiqiy fikrlashni rivojlantirish	42
Dauekeeva Gulistan Orinbaevna	
Talabalarga ingliz tilidagi matnlarni kommunikativ metod yordamida o'qish texnikasini takomillashtirish usullari	46
Mo'minova Mahliyo Axrorjonovna	
Velosiped haydashning afzalliklari.....	49
Raxmonova Go'zal Bobir qizi	
Компетентностный подход как стратегическая основа модернизации образования и его реализация в преподавании русского языка как иностранного в Узбекистане	54
Мирзакбарова Севда Вахиддиновна	
Umumta'lim maktablarida texnologiya fani mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari va metodlari.....	58
Ziyamova Gulbaxor Tulabayevna	
Типы аббревиации в русском и узбекском языках: сравнительно-типологический анализ.....	62
Рахмонова Бахтигул Пайзилловна	
Maktabgacha ta'limda nutqni rivojlantirish jarayonida didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish metodikasi	65
Abidjonova Mushtariybonu Qobiljon qizi	
Tarbiyaviy tadbirlarni samarali tashkil etishda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti va ota-onalarning o'zaro hamkorlik masalalari.....	71
Sanayeva Surayyo Bobonazarovna, Jabborova Shaxina G'affor qizi	
Qadriyatli yondashuv asosida talabalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish ..	76
G'aybullayev Quvonchbek G'olibovich	
Maktab o'quvchilarida stressga barqarorlik namoyon bo'lishining psixologik tahlili	83
Ismoilova N. Z.	
Yoshlar ma'naviyatini shakllantirishda milliy qadriyatlarning o'rni.....	87
Karshiyev Jaxongir Abdirayimovich	
Funksional savodxonlikni rivojlantirishda o'qish savodxonligining o'rni va ahamiyati	91
Xatamova Munisa Mamadulla qizi	
Transformatsiyalash tizimi asosida o'quvchilarning loyihalash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish samaradorligi.....	95
Jurayeva Zulayxo Islomovna	
Zamonaviy boshqaruv nazariyalarida rahbar muloqoti (transformatsion, kommunikativ va ishtirokchi boshqaruv yondashuvlari asosida).....	102
Islamova Dildar Dilshodovna	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida pedagogik kompetentlikni tabaqalashgan yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish mazmuni	107
Begmatova Nasiba Mengnarovna	
Bo'lajak maxsus pedagoglarni inklyuziv ta'limda subyektlar faoliyatini o'rgatish metodikasi	112
Dilshodov Abrorjon Dilshodjon o'g'li	
Pre-Reading Activities to Enhance Foreign Language Reading Comprehension: Reading "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer" in 10–11 Grades	118
Djumaniyazova Zulfiya Kaliyevna	
Nutq aktlarini o'rgatishda autentik materiallardan foydalanishning metodik imkoniyatlari (filologik yo'nalish talabalari misolida)	122
Fayzulloeva Chevar G'ayrat qizi	
Yangi O'zbekistonda talaba-yoshlarni milliy yuksaltirishda jadid-marifatparvarlari ilgari surgan g'oyalarning o'rni va roli	125
Mamadaliyev Abduvoxid Maxsitaliyevich	
Gimnastikaning O'zbekistonga kirib kelish va rivojlanish tarixi	128
N. Q. Mamasidova	
Uglevodorodlar tarkibini aniqlashda massa ulushiga asoslangan reflektiv yondashuv (7-9-sinflar misolida)	131
Maxamadiyev Sharofiddin Jumaboyevich, Smanova Zulayxo Asanalievna	
Screencasting materiallarini yaratish va ularni o'quv jarayonida qo'llash	134
Maxmudova Dilfuza Meliyevna, Ergashov Niyozxon Ilyozxon o'g'li	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda so'z shakllanishini psixolingvistik asoslari	137
Moxirabonu G'aniyeva Adxam qizi	
Maktabgacha ta'limdagi muammolar va yechimlar: o'zbekiston respublikasi tajribasi	140
N. Sh. Miryusupova	
Interaktiv kartografik resurslar va ularning ta'lim jarayonida qo'llanilishining didaktik, kognitiv hamda metodik asoslari	143
Olimova Aziza Abdullayevna	
Mentorlik tizimining tarixiy ildizlari va rivojlanish bosqichlari	147
Oxunova Dilnoza Qaxxorjonovna, Abdumannonova Durdonaxon Shuxratjon qizi	
Talabalarning psixologik holati va stress omillarining prokrastinatsiyaga ta'siri hamda mustaqil ta'lim faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlash usullari	150
Razakov Farxod Kuvondikovich, Rajabov Hikmat Toshevich	
Talabalarni stulda o'tirgan qiyofachi portreti ranglavhasini ishlashga o'rgatish metodikasi	154
Sadatov Chori Xolmuradovich	
Organik kimyo fanini o'qitishda teskari ta'lim va texnologiyalarning ahamiyati	158
Umrbekova Maftuna Ulug'bek qizi, Babanazarova Ayzada Omirbaevna, Abdulkakimova Gulziyba Ziyatdinovna	
Duduqlanishni bartaraf etishda kompleks metodlarini qo'llashning samaradorligi	162
Xasanova Barnoxon Abdusattor qizi	
Shaxsga yo'naltirilgan yondashuv asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogik kompetentligini takomillashtirish	165
Xolbozorova Nasiba Xolbozar qizi	
Проектирование персонализированных образовательных сценариев в дошкольном образовании средствами генеративного искусственного интеллекта	168
Пак Диана Александровна	
Bo'lajak pedagoglarni tayyorlashda STEAM yondashuvining roli	170
Atenov Jandarbek Dayrabay o'g'li	
Innovatsion ta'lim muhitida talabalarning kasbiy muloqot kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik asoslari	173
Bo'ltakov Sanjarbek Xazratqul o'g'li	
Alohida ta'lim ehtiyojlari mavjud bo'lgan bolalar uchun inklyuziv ta'lim tizimining ahamiyati	176
Mehmonova Nodiraxon Yusufxon qizi	

Duduqlanish nutq kamchiligini korreksiyalashning maxsus va integratsiyalashgan texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish.....	180
Boxodirova Gulasaxon Ibrohimovna	
Эссе как инструмент формирования и диагностики компетенций в системе высшего образования .	184
Шейхмамбетов Сервер Рефикович	
Matallar va folklor hikoyalari: maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida interaktiv dars texnologiyalari.....	188
Azimova Nodira Hikmatovna	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda jismoniy sifatlarni rivojlantirish va ularni sportga yo'naltirishning pedagogik asoslari.....	191
Norboyev Komiljon Jurakulovich, Rustamova Kamola Xayrulla qizi	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning o'qitilishining ahamiyati.....	194
Burkhanova Sabo Tulanovna	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida O'zbekistonning eng yangi tarixini o'qitishning metodologik asoslari va muammolari	197
Norbutayeva Guzal Abdig'ofurovna	
Ta'lim tashkilotlarida sifatni boshqarish jarayonlarini tizimli rejalashtirishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari.....	200
Abdurashit Karimovich Avliyakov	
Tarbiya darslari samaradorligini oshirishda abdulla avloniy pedagogik hikmatlaridan foydalanishni metodik tashkil etish.....	204
Daliyeva Eliza Zokir qizi	
Badiiy-tarixiy meros asosida bo'lajak pedagoglarning refleksiv tafakkuri va kasbiy identifikatsiyasini rivojlantirish	207
Qodirova Mavluda Maxodir qizi	
Adabiyot darslarida lirik asarlarni vizual yondashuvlar asosida o'qitish usullari.....	210
Sobitova Mahmudaxon Shuxratbek qizi	
ESG tamoyillarini ta'lim tizimiga joriy etish orqali talabalarda ekologik, ijtimoiy va boshqaruv ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	216
Tursunova Shahzoda Baxromovna	
Социально-психологические факторы нарушения психологического здоровья в семье	219
Гулру Тургунова	
O'zini tarbiyalash (self-development) g'oyasining Ibn Sino ta'limotidagi o'rni	229
Usmanova E'zoza Zokirjonovna	
Оценка динамики физиологических показателей волейболистов 12–16 лет в предсоревновательный и соревновательный периоды	234
Умматалиева Шерзода Шерали угли	
Individual sport turlarida sportchilarning natijadorlik kompetensiyasini motivatsion omillar asosida shakllantirish.....	239
Baratov Nasriddin Karshibayevich	
O'smirlarda internetdan ortiqcha foydalanishning psixologik oqibatlarini	243
Fayziyeva Nodira Sobirovna	
Transakt analiz: shaxslararo muloqotni tahlil qilishning nazariy va amaliy asoslari	247
Nilufar Sayfidinovna Sangirova	
Inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonini boshqarish mexanizmlarini rivojlantirish (umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari misolida)	252
Abdug'aniyev Abdurauf Abdumannonovich	
O'zbek milliy kurashining tarixiy rivojlanish bosqichlari va uning yoshlar tarbiyasidagi pedagogik ahamiyati.....	257
Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Almardanov Xasan Asqarovich	
Belbog'li kurashning shakllanishi va rivojlanish tarixi: jismoniy tarbiya tizimidagi o'rni va metodik imkoniyatlari	261
Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Norqizilov Muxammadbek Sherali o'gli	

Dzyudo kurashining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi va uning ta'lim jarayonida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida qo'llanishi	265
<i>Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Norqobilov Jamshid G'ulomovich</i>	
Dzyudo kurashining tarixiy evolyutsiyasi va uning ta'lim jarayonida kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida qo'llanishi	270
<i>Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi, Nurullayev Fazliddin Murodulla o'gli</i>	
Raqamli muhitda shaxs xulq-atvori dinamikasi (bolalik va o'smirlilik misolida)	275
<i>Raimdjanov Mirkarim Tolibjon o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarning intellektual qobiliyatlarini oshirishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari	278
<i>Suvanova Baxtigul Baxridinovna</i>	
Xalqaro tajriba asosida o'quvchilarda tadbirkorlik ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish mexanizmlari.....	283
<i>Azimov I. T., Mirzayeva N. I.</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda ingliz tili o'qitishda didaktik vositalardan foydalanish	288
<i>Ziyaboyeva Sevara Saydullayevna</i>	
Yuqori malakali o'rta masofaga yuguruvchilarning jismoniy rivojlanish dinamikasi	292
<i>Nazarov Nuriddin Baxranovich</i>	
Maktab direktorining partisipativ boshqaruv faoliyatida qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonida ishtirokchilarning roli	297
<i>Jabborova Yulduzxon Hasan qizi</i>	
Tibbiyotda nizoli vaziyatlar va ularni bartaraf etish usullari.....	301
<i>Olimova Dono Shakirovna, Baxtiyorova Shahnoza Mansurbekovna</i>	
Ichki kasalliklarni tashxislashda klinik fikrlashning o'rni.....	304
<i>Tilavova Muqaddas, Hasanova Munisa, Mamatqulova Fayzo, Hakimova Xonbuvi Hakimovna</i>	
Транснациональные компании и проблема суверенитета национального государства.....	307
<i>Ф. Равшанов, Л. Сохибова</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarda o'quv-biluv faoliyati motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishning pedagogik ahamiyati	311
<i>Muhammadiyeva Manzura Maratovna, Musulmonova Sabrina Akmal qizi</i>	
Texnologik ta'limda xorijiy tajriba	316
<i>Lochinbek Abdirasulov</i>	
Talabalarda ilmiy-tadqiqot ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	319
<i>Saffarova Mohidil Axmadovna, Mustafayeva Feruza Anvar qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining ona tili darslaridagi asosiy resurslari: "ona tili" darsligi, mashq daftari, o'qituvchi kitobi ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishning muhim omili sifatida.....	324
<i>Soatova Hilola Shuhrat qizi</i>	
Harbiy vatanparvarlik tarbiyasi – zamonaviy jamiyat taraqqiyotining muhim omili sifatida.....	328
<i>R. D. Mustayev, H. F. Abduvositov</i>	
Русскоязычная литература Узбекистана современного периода: проблематика, поэтика и художественный анализ	332
<i>Чернова Татьяна Алексеевна</i>	
O'smirlar orasida tengdoshlar bosimi va uning psixologik ta'siri	335
<i>Toshpo'latova O'giloy Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak tarbiyachilarning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda iste'mol madaniyatini shakllantirish jarayonida targeting yondashuvining pedagogik nazariy asoslari	339
<i>D. G. Umnov</i>	
Ona tili darslarini ikkinchi til tamoyillari asosida tashkil etish masalalari.....	344
<i>Maxkamova Guluzroxon Abdumutalibovna</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida mustaqil ishlarni pedagogik jihatlardan tashkil etishning nazariy va amaliy aspektlari	347
<i>Mahkamov Mahammadjon Dadajonovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinflarda interfaol metodlar asosida dars jarayonini takomillashtirish metodikasi	351
<i>Muhammadjonova Durdonaxon Bahromjon qizi</i>	
Tarix darslarini modellashtirishda pedagogik metodlar tasnifi va ularning samaradorligi	354
<i>Ikrom Qodirov</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS	Hadassah hospital maktabi modelining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, pedagogik samaradorligi va uni O'zbekiston hospital maktablariga tatbiq etishning ahamiyati 357 <i>Abdullayev Aziz Habibullayevich, Ochilov Orazbek Qosim o'g'li, Alimova Dono Abbosxonovna</i>
	Davlat boshqaruvi tizimida korrupsiyaviy xavf-xatarlarni baholash va prognozlash metodologiyasi..... 361 <i>Amirxo'jayev Shukurjon Qurbonovich, Sotvoldiyev Akbarjon Umidjon o'g'li</i>
	Neyropedagogik yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarda pozitiv fikrlashni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy va amaliy asoslari 364 <i>Babakulova Dilnoza Ramazonovna</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinflarda nutqiy nuqsonlarning oldini olish va o'quvchilarning talaffuz madaniyatini shakllantirish metodikasi 367 <i>Baxtiyorova Nastarin Baxriddinovna, Daminova Dilbar Melimurodovna</i>
	Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining bilim olishga qiziqishini oshirishda gamifikatsiya elementlaridan foydalanishning nazariy-metodik asoslari 370 <i>G'aniyeva Gulxayyo Islom qizi, Raxmatova Shaxlo Mansurovna</i>
	Ingliz tili darslarida kitobxonlik ko'nikmalarining o'ziga xosligi 373 <i>Jo'raboyeva Turg'unoy Ikromjon qizi</i>
	Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarida lingvokognitiv kompetentlikni rivojlantirishning didaktik tizimi..... 377 <i>Kozimova Sadoqat</i>
	Umumta'lim maktablarida tabiiy fanlar (science)ni o'qitish orqali ekologik savodxonlikni shakllantirishning pedagogik asoslari 380 <i>Majitov Turg'unali Anvar o'g'li</i>
	Oilaviy munosabatlarda manipulyativ muloqot indikatsiyasi: psixologik tahlil va eksperimental natijalar 383 <i>Nishanova Zulfizar Yashin qizi</i>
	Bo'lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy tayyorgarligini takomillashtirishda raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalarining o'rni 386 <i>Nurulloyev Firuz No'monjonovich</i>
	Talabalarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini shakllantirishning tarixiy-pedagogik asoslari (ma'rifatparvar mutafakkirlar merosi misolida)..... 390 <i>Sabirov Kaxramon Bektursun o'g'li</i>
	Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshidagi 5-6 yoshli bolalarda muammoli vaziyatlarni mustaqil yechish qobiliyatini shakllantirish metodikasini takomillashtirish 393 <i>Tillayeva Vasila O'ktam qizi</i>
	Kritik fikrlash kompetensiyasining pedagogik va didaktik mazmuni 398 <i>Tursunaliyev Shaxzod Sherali o'g'li</i>
	Kurashchi qizlarning texnik harakatlarini kinematik va kinetik modellashtirish 402 <i>Xomudjonova Feruza Komiljon qizi</i>
	Oliy ta'limda ishga doir muloqot asoslari fanini o'qitish orqali talabalarning og'zaki fikrlash va nutq faoliyatini rivojlantirish 406 <i>Yuldasheva Dilnoza Bekmurodovna</i>
	Роль онлайн-платформ и образовательных сервисов в формировании ответственности студентов. 409 <i>Гуламов Жасур Баходирович</i>
	Изучение изменений полярного переключения негативных и позитивных эмоций среднего воздействия в процессе развития/реабилитации механизмов эмпатии 413 <i>Ягудин Дмитрий Рустамович</i>
	Produktiv nutq ko'nikmalari orqali nutq aktlarini o'qitish samaradorligi..... 421 <i>Sadikov Erkin Tursunovich</i>
	Проблемы формирования письменной коммуникативной компетенции у студентов выпускных курсов высших учебных заведений 424 <i>Раджабова Зебинисо Анваровна</i>
	Pedagogika sohasida yangi ilmiy yo'nalish – pedagogik innovatsiya 427 <i>M.U. Raxmanova</i>

Muammoli o'qitish asosida kichik maktab yoshidagi o'quvchilarning ijodiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish.....	431
<i>Giyasova Shaxnoza Abdurafikovna</i>	
9–10 yoshli o'quvchilar orasidagi nizolarni korreksion yondashuv bilan boshqarish	435
<i>Qulmatov Sindorqul Ibragimovich, Yarbekova Yulduz Bahromjon qizi</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda raqamli mediakompetentlikni rivojlantirish	439
<i>Mo'minova Madina, Mamasodiqova Saida</i>	
Разработка приложения для визуализации и анализа решения задач линейного программирования.....	442
<i>Маматов Ислонбек Ильесович, Буронова Муниса Баходировна</i>	
Mustaqil ta'lim topshiriqlarini integrativ modellashtirish tashkiliy-metodik muammo sifatida	448
<i>Ibroximova O'g'iloy Inomjon qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda axloqiy tarbiyani baholash va "tarbiya kundaligi"ni joriy etish metodikasi.....	451
<i>Norimboyeva Sarvinoz Abror qizi, Norimboyeva Sarvinoz Abror qizi</i>	
Talabalarda vatanparvarlik fazilatlarini rivojlantirishning nazariy-pedagogik va didaktik asoslari.....	456
<i>Xaydaraliyev Xurshid Xamidullayevich</i>	
Zamonaviy yosh oilalarda gender munosabatining o'rganilganlik holati	462
<i>Abduqayumova Gulnoza Karimjon qizi</i>	
Arifmetik progressiyani o'qitishda "progressiya konstruktori" amaliy-tadqiqot metodining samaradorligi....	466
<i>Abdurahmonova Zamira Raxmatullayevna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim yo'nalishi talabalarining kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirishning mazmuni.....	471
<i>Ashurova To'lg'anoy Ergashevna</i>	
Onlayn shaxmat platformalarining boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari tafakkuriga ta'siri	475
<i>Boboqulov Chori Urolovich</i>	
Ta'lim tizimida boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirish.....	480
<i>Kadirkulov Dilmurod Alimahamedovich</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda muloqot madaniyatini shakllantirish mezonlari.....	485
<i>Mirsagatova Nargiza Sayfullayevna</i>	
Communicative Language Teaching in Modern Classrooms: Strengths, Limitations, and Pedagogical Implications	490
<i>Mirzaliyeva Sarvinoz</i>	
Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasasi talabalarining fizikadan metodik faoliyatga tayyorgarligini rivojlantirish	493
<i>Murtazayev Zohid Murtazayevich</i>	
Zo'ravonlikning inson ruhiyatiga salbiy ta'siri va oqibatlari	497
<i>Mutabarxon Maxsudova</i>	
STEM ta'limi sharoitida o'quvchilarning texnik tafakkurini rivojlantirishning transdisiplinar metodik modeli	501
<i>Normuxamedov Zarif</i>	
Jadidchilar asarlarida boshlang'ich ta'limga oid pedagogik qarashlarning nazariy asoslari	507
<i>Sariboyeva Aziza G'apur qizi</i>	
Pedagogika tarixida dars samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha qarashlar va amaliyotdagi innovatsion loyihalar tahlili.....	510
<i>To'raqulova Feruza Jobir qizi</i>	
Yosh qizlarda shaxsiy mustaqillik va oilaviy mas'uliyat muvozanati	514
<i>To'xtamatova Nargiza, Boltaboyeva Marg'uba</i>	
Individual dars mashg'ulotlari orqali boksning faolligini aniqlash xususiyatlari	517
<i>Usmonov Mansur Qurbonmurotovich</i>	
Преимущества и недостатки использования виртуальных лабораторных работ по физике	522
<i>Тилова Турдихол Баратовна</i>	
Neyrolingvistik dasturlashning (NLD) nazariy va amaliy jihatlari	529
<i>Xolikova Dilobarxon Maxsitovna</i>	

Tabiiy fanlar darslarini o'qitishda muammoli texnologiyalardan foydalanish usullari	533
<i>Ochilova O'g'iloy Mardon qizi</i>	
Communicative-Pragmatic Analysis of Binary-Based Paremias in English, Uzbek, and Russian Languages.....	537
<i>Jumanova Sabrina Vaydullo kizi</i>	
Kurash mashg'ulotlarida raqamli texnologiyalar qo'llanilishi.....	542
<i>Melikuziyev Azizjon Adaxamjon o'g'li</i>	
O'spirinlarda kasbiy tanlov noaniqligi sharoitida mustaqil qarorlarni rivojlantirishning psixologik xususiyatlari	546
<i>Karimova Gulxumor Shodi qizi</i>	
ChatGPT kabi til modellarining ta'lim va fan sohasiga ta'siri	550
<i>Djabbarova Xabiba Kuvandikovna</i>	
Biologiya ta'limida qo'llaniladigan masala va mashqlarning turlari, mazmuni va kreativlikni rivojlantirishdagi o'rni	554
<i>Yusupova Lobar Nizomjon qizi, Raxmatov Uchkun Ergashevich</i>	
Сравнительный анализ русской и узбекской концептосфер в контексте преподавания РКИ.....	560
<i>Рустамова Феруза Махмуджановна</i>	
Professional ta'lim muassasalari o'quvchilarining kasbiy madaniyatini kompetensiyaviy yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish texnologiyalari	565
<i>Imomov Musurmon Pirnazarovich</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda aksiologik qadriyatlar va raqamli kompetensiyalarni uyg'un rivojlantirish metodikasi.....	572
<i>Shabbazova Dilfuza Ruzikulovna</i>	
Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy ijodkorligini rivojlantirishda klaster integratsiyasi va refleksiv yondashuvning o'rni	576
<i>Shabbazova Nodira Xamzayevna</i>	
Umumta'lim maktablarida immersiv texnologiyalar imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish	579
<i>Axmedova Dilnoza Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Tasviriy san'at ta'limida kompozitsiya o'qitishning takomillashtirilgan metodik tizimi.....	581
<i>Karshiboyeva Dilafuz Boxodirovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ona tili o'qituvchilarining og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirishda refleksiv topshiriqlarning o'rni .	584
<i>Altibayeva Malika Kuvandikovna</i>	
STEAM yondashuvi asosida rivojlantiruvchi markazlarning samaradorligini oshirish yo'nalishlari.....	587
<i>O'rinova Feruza O'ljayevna, To'xtaboyeva Maftunaxon G'aniyevna</i>	
Aholi o'rtasida ommaviy sportni rivojlantirishning ilmiy-uslubiy asoslari.....	591
<i>Davulov Ozodbek Qalandarovich</i>	
Tasavvufda ma'naviy tarbiya tushunchasi va uning nazariy-metodologik asoslari.....	595
<i>Satimova Sevinch Sardorbekovna</i>	
Teaching Literary and Non-Literary Forms of Speech to Young Learners.....	600
<i>Nargiza Tulyaganova</i>	
Pedagog kadrlarni innovatsion faoliyatga tayyorlashni boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirishning metod va mexanizmlari	604
<i>Aziboyev Shuhrat Olimovich</i>	
Cerebral falajli bolalarda sensor, diqqat va motor funksiyalar integratsiyasining faktorli tahlili	608
<i>Karimberdiyev Azamat Axmadjon o'g'li</i>	
O'smirlik davrida emotsional intellektni namoyon bo'lishining psixologik xususiyatlari	614
<i>Djumabaeva Manzura Bagibekovna, Zoirova Laylo Alisher qizi, Umirboyeva Zaxro Dilmurod qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy ta'lim modellari mohiyati va ularning pedagogik tizimdagi o'rni (4K, 5E, 5I modellari misolida).....	617
<i>Raxmatov Uchkun Ergashevich, Qodirova Marjona Azamat qizi</i>	
Ayollarni iqtisodiy faollikka tayyorlashda o'quv dasturlarini loyihalash tamoyillari	624
<i>Diyarova Shaxloxon Rovshan qizi</i>	

Interfaol ta'lim metodlari asosida o'qituvchilarning kreativlik qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish metodikasi: tajriba-sinov natijalari tahlili	628
<i>Abdiyeva Shodiyona Yodgor qizi</i>	
Raqamli muhitda maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyalanuvchilarining qo'shimcha ta'limini tashkil etish: tadqiqotlar sharhi	633
<i>Amanova Dilorom Faxritdin qizi</i>	
Kognitiv tilshunoslikda skript atamasi va uning voqelanish mexanizmlari	637
<i>Fayzullayev Shohrux</i>	
The Concept of Blended Learning and its Role in the Modern Educational Paradigm	641
<i>Fozilova Maxina Adashevna</i>	
Finlyandiya boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matematika fanini o'qitish metodikasi	645
<i>G'aybulloyeva Yulduz Mexriddinovna</i>	
Xalq hunarmandchiligi bo'yicha o'quvchilarning kreativ qobiliyatini rivojlantirish	651
<i>Isoqov Shohruh Turabek o'g'li</i>	
Communicative-Pragmatic Analysis of Binary-Based Paremias in English, Uzbek, and Russian Languages	654
<i>Jumanova Sabrina Vaydullo kizi</i>	
Internet-risk profilaktikasining bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni tayyorlashdagi o'rni	659
<i>Mamatxanova Nargiza Toxirovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida inklyuziv ta'limni samarali tashkil etishning psixologik-pedagogik shart-sharoitlari	663
<i>N. Sh. Abdullayeva, F. R.Valiyeva, S. S. Raximova</i>	
Musiqiy-ritmik harakatlarning asosiy komponentlari va ularni rivojlantirishda SI imkoniyatlari	667
<i>O. A. Shodiyeva</i>	
Oliy ta'lim muassasalarida kredit-modul tizimi asosida ta'limni tashkil etishning pedagogik xususiyatlari ..	672
<i>Y. R. Azzamov</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida integratsion yondashuv asosida bolalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashning pedagogik asoslari	676
<i>Yakubova Zilola Zikirovna</i>	
Aksiologik yondashuv asosida talabalarda mas'uliyatni rivojlantirish pedagogik muammo sifatida	679
<i>Teshayeva Dilnoza Chori qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida bolalarni tasviriy faoliyat turlari asosida estetik tarbiyalash masalalari.	684
<i>Yuldasheva Dilshoda To'lqinovna</i>	
Профессиональная рефлексия как фактор развития научного интеллекта будущего педагога в системе педагогического образования	688
<i>Анварова Хуснора, Isoxоnova Aziza</i>	
Толерантность в мультикультурном обществе	692
<i>Бекбосынова З. К.</i>	
Методика работы над ошибками как средство повышения грамотности	696
<i>Исмаилова Мадинабону</i>	
Методы и подходы к развитию профессиональной лексической компетенции студентов военных направлений	701
<i>Хамидова Нигора Тулкуновна</i>	
Raqamli ta'lim muhiti va uning maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar rivojiga ta'siri	704
<i>Xayriddinova Parvinabonu Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida "botanika" fanini o'qitish samaradorligini oshirishda elektron ta'lim resurslardan foydalanish metodikasini takomillashtirish	707
<i>Nasirova Shahlo Qutbiddinovna</i>	
Maktabgacha katta yoshdagi bolalarning intellektual va ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda media ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning o'ziga xosligi	710
<i>Mahmudjanova Ro'za Mahmudjan qizi</i>	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

O'zbekistonda jismoniy tarbiya va ommaviy sport samaradorligining tahliliy jihatlari.....	714
<i>Aslanova Malohat Akramovna</i>	
Differensial yondashuv asosida o'quvchilarning moliyaviy savodxonligini rivojlantirish muhim omil sifatida.....	718
<i>Mirzayev Akramjon O'ktamjonovich, Xokimjonova Feruza Hosiljon qizi</i>	
Jismoniy tarbiya-sog'lomlashtirish faoliyati jarayonida oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining sog'lom turmush tarzini shakllantirish	721
<i>Ne'matova Diyora Dilshod qizi</i>	
Sport gimnastikasining yoshlar jismoniy rivojlanishidagi o'rni va ahamiyati	725
<i>Pirimova Nargiza Adilovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi (3–6 yosh) bolalarda erta ingliz tili o'rganishning psixologik va pedagogik samaradorligi.....	728
<i>Xayrullayeva Muharramxon Davronbek qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim sifati va samaradorligini oshirishning strategik yo'nalishlari	733
<i>Otahanova Manzura G'ofurovna</i>	
Development of Intercultural Communication Competence of Future Teachers in Speaking Classes as an Important Lingvodidactic Problem: Evidence From Uzbekistan's Higher Education Context.....	736
<i>Muhammadiyeva Halima Saidahmadovna</i>	
Bo'lajak ona tili o'qituvchilarining og'zaki va yozma nutqini rivojlantirishda reflektiv topshiriqlarning o'rni .	749
<i>Altibayeva Malika Kuvandikovna</i>	
Jamiyatda huquqiy madaniyatni shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda davlat hokimiyati organlari faoliyatini takomillashtirish muammolari va istiqbollari	752
<i>Ismailov Sarvarbek Anvarbekovich, Maxkamova Munavvarxon Alisher qizi</i>	
Psixolog talabalarda kasbiy refleksiyaning rivojlantirishning tarbiyaviy-psixologik determinantlari: muammolar va yechimlar	757
<i>Shukurova Nargiza Ikramovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida valeologik madaniyatni rivojlantirishda jismoniy tarbiyaning pedagogik salohiyati	762
<i>Xudoyberdiyev Sh. M.</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar intellektual qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishda ta'lim metodlari va vositalari.....	766
<i>Esanbekova Fotima G'ayratjonovna</i>	
Чеховские традиции в прозе XX века (Бунин, Платонов, Шукшин)	770
<i>Багирова Паринисо Бобировна</i>	
Oliy ta'limda mustaqil ishlarni tashkillashtirishda nostandart testlardan foydalanishning samarali metodlari va metodik tavsiyalar.....	775
<i>Nurnazarova Gavharoy Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Umumta'lim va ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab o'quvchilarida oila obrazining kognitiv va emotsional komponentlari qiyosiy tahlili	780
<i>Toshtemirova Nigora Ibrohimovna</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf "Tarbiya" darsligida Abdulla Avloniyning "Turkiy guliston yoxud axloq" asari g'oyalari integratsiyalashning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	784
<i>Tovoshova Ozoda Akmal qizi</i>	
Noto'liq oila farzandlarida emotsional-irodaviy sohani rivojlantirish orqali ijtimoiy deadaptatsiyani bartaraf etish.....	789
<i>Kaxarova Ozoda Abdimominovna</i>	
Kelajak pedagog shaxsini rivojlantirishda axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarining psixologik ta'siri...	793
<i>M. B. Pulatova</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida inson resurslarini boshqarish tushunchasining ilmiy-nazariy tahlili	796
<i>Maraimova Muxtabar Pulatovna</i>	
Kredit-modul modeli asosida kreativ ta'lim muhitini yaratish omillari va imkoniyatlari.....	801
<i>Xalkuziyeva Dilnoza Baxodirovna</i>	

Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagoglarining kasbiy faoliyati samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan pedagogik texnologiya modeli	805
<i>G'aniyeva Vazira Yusufvna</i>	
Xorijiy va mahalliy tajribada prognostik madaniyatni shakllantirish yondashuvlari	809
<i>Ziyoda Urinbayeva</i>	
The Role of Tolerance in the Professional Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies	813
<i>Toshpo'latov Anvar Shokir o'g'li</i>	
O'quvchilarni milliy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalashda sharq mutaffakirlari merosidan foydalanish	818
<i>Eshquvvatov To'liqinjon Eshquvvatovich, Buronova Durdona Erkin qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda interfaol metodlar orqali integrativ faoliyatlarni tashkil etish	822
<i>Kubayeva Mavluda Baxtiyor qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim jarayonida mantiqiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari	826
<i>Mirzaqobilova Sarvinoz Aliqul qizi</i>	
Zamonaviy jamiyatda ekologik mediamadaniyatni shakllantirish masalalari	832
<i>Marziyayev Janabay Kalibayevich</i>	
Alisher Navoiyning "Mahlub ul-qulub" asari asosida o'quvchilarning axloqiy fazilatlarini shakllantirish	836
<i>Karamatova Dilfuza Sadinovna, Mahmudova Niginabonu Mizrof qizi, Ravshanova Mohinur O'tkir qizi</i>	
Pedagogik amaliyot jarayonida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning kasbiy karyera loyihalash ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish	840
<i>Djalolova Sevara Xolmurodovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotida inklyuziv ta'limni tashkil etishda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar	845
<i>G'ulomova Dildora Shoirvna</i>	
Rus tilini o'qitishda grammatik kompetensiyani kommunikativ metod yordamida shakllantirish: qoidalardan jonli muloqotga o'tish metodikasi	850
<i>Arabova Muhiba Bazarovna</i>	
Bo'lajak musiqa o'qituvchisining kasbiy kompetentligini axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari asosida takomillashtirishning pedagogik muammo va ehtiyojlari	854
<i>Axrorova Munajat Mashraf qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida tanqidiy tafakkur ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishning pedagogik xususiyatlari	858
<i>Azizjonova Asilabonu Alisher qizi</i>	
Ta'limda innovatsion yondashuvlarning pedagogik-psixologik asoslari (pedagogik otm misolida).....	862
<i>Begmatova Dildora Saydaliyevna</i>	
Developing the Creativity of Primary School Students Through Art-Pedagogical Methods	866
<i>Dauletmuratova Bayramgul Makhsetbay kizi</i>	
Tabiiy fanlar darslarida kreativ ta'lim muhitini shakllantirishning innovatsion texnologiyalari va ularni takomillashtirish yo'llari	871
<i>Farmanova Parvina Jamshid qizi</i>	
Raqamli texnologiyalar yordamida arifmetik ko'nikmalarni mustahkamlash: zamonaviy ta'limdagi innovatsion yondashuvlar.....	875
<i>Izimbetova Amina</i>	
Matematika va o'yinlar nazariyasi: strategik qarorlarni modellashtirishda rivojlanish bosqichlari va amaliy ahamiyati.....	878
<i>Jumanazarova Shahzada</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'qish faoliyatini rivojlantirishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari	881
<i>Laylo Berdiqulova Erkin qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilari nutqini integrativ yondashuv asosida o'stirish usullari.....	885
<i>Mamatraimova Dilshoda Chorshanbiyevna, Normengliyeva Sevinch Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
STEAM texnologiyasi vositasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda kreativlikni rivojlantirish tamoyillari	889
<i>Nazirova Guzal Malikovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda maishiy ko'nikmalarni takomillashtirishning ilmiy nazariy asoslari.....	893
<i>Saydaliyeva Gavhar Burxon qizi</i>	

Fizika fanini o'qitishda formativ baholash asosida o'quvchilarning tanqidiy fikrlash kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish	896
<i>Sobirov Avazbek Anvarovich</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ayrim emotsional holatlar (injiqlik va emotsional reaktivlik)ni boshqarish.....	903
<i>Sultonova Nurxon Anvarovna</i>	
Teatr pedagogikasi asosida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning ijodiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirish modeli va metodlari	907
<i>Tolipova Shohista Qudrat qizi</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida emotsional intellektni rivojlantirishda didaktik o'yinlarning roli	911
<i>Turg'unova Gulzoda Botir qizi</i>	
Farzand tarbiyasida onaning psixologik va axloqiy ta'sirining amaliy jihatlari	916
<i>Tuxtaboyeva Durdonaxon Tulkunovna</i>	
Ontogenezning turli bosqichlarida shaxsning axloqiy rivojlanish xususiyatlari	919
<i>Umaraliyev Muzaffarjon Muhammadjon o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarining o'zlashtirishini metakognitiv monitoring qilish va baholashning nazariy-metodik asoslari	923
<i>Xalikova Zaxro Mirshadmanovna</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt texnologiyalarining psixologiyada qo'llanilishi	927
<i>Yoqubova Gulhayo Erkin qizi</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	931
<i>Bilolov Inomjon O'ktamovich</i>	
Karatening kelib chiqish tarixi	934
<i>Isayev Saidaliddinxon Islom o'g'li</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida kreativ faollikni shakllantirishga doir usul va vositalar	937
<i>Nishonova Kamola Shokirjon qizi, Mamadjonova Hayotxon Abduolim qizi</i>	
Родительские установки и развитие личности	941
<i>Кодирова Нилуфар Абдусаттор кизи</i>	
Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida matnni tushunish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish metodikasi	945
<i>Yusupova Umida</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda liderlik va tashabbuskorlik sifatlarini rivojlantirish mexanizmlari	950
<i>Kadirova Omaxon Sobirjonovna</i>	
Maktab ta'limi tizimida raqamli boshqaruv modelini joriy etish orqali ta'lim sifatini oshirish	954
<i>Raxmatova Xurshida G'ofurovna, Tangirov Xurram Ergashevich</i>	
Особенности влияния психолога дошкольной образовательной организации на психическое развитие ребенка в игровой среде	961
<i>Камолдинова Диёра Жалолиддин қизи</i>	
Boshlang'ich maktabda sog'lom ijtimoiy-pedagogik muhitni shakllantirish yo'llari.....	968
<i>Fayzidinova Maxsuda Akmalovna</i>	
Maktabgacha ta'limda ma'naviy-axloqiy kompetentlikni shakllantirish: milliy va xalqaro pedagogik yondashuvlar	971
<i>N. R. Dushayeva</i>	
O'qish savodxonligini rivojlantirishda o'quvchilarning individual profili asosida moslashtirilgan didaktik yondashuvlarni ishlab chiqish.....	975
<i>Oripova Dilnozaxon Abduvosi qizi</i>	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida oliy ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish strategiyalari	980
<i>Rabbimova Munisxon Mustafoyevna</i>	
O'qitishda san'at vositalaridan foydalanish genezisi va zamonaviy tajribalari.....	983
<i>Suvanova Kamola Raimqul qizi</i>	
Sun'iy intellekt muhitida ta'lim olish jarayonida talabalarning psixofiziologik holati va kognitiv yuklamasini baholash	989
<i>Turayeva Irodaxon Lochinbek qizi</i>	

Bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarning konfliktologik kompetentlikni rivojlantirish – dolzarb pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	993
<i>Xadicha Muxammadiyeva Karomatovna, R. Rayimova</i>	
The Influence of Digitalization on Written Communication.....	998
<i>Yusupova Sitara Ashuraliyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'lim o'qish savodxonligi va ona tili darslariga zamonaviy yondashuvlar.....	1002
<i>G'oyibnazarova Nargiza Raximjonovna</i>	
O'quvchilarning ijodiy ish faoliyati malakalarni shakllantirishga mos masalalarni tanlash metodlari.....	1005
<i>Artiqov Maqsud Bahodirovich, Sherimmatova Mahfuza Rasul qizi, Sarsenbayeva Zilola Kamiljon qizi</i>	
Mashq va topshiriqlar tizimi – fonetik ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish tizimi.....	1011
<i>Ganiyeva Dildora Sagdullayevna</i>	
Psixologik treninglarning uslubiy muammolari: nazariy va amaliy tahlil.....	1015
<i>Gulchehra Utamurodova Narbayevna</i>	
O'quvchilarning kreativ fikrlashlarini rivojlantirishda mental xaritalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	1018
<i>Islamova Karima Turdiyevna</i>	
Pedagogning kasbiy rivojlanishi va o'zaro xamkorlik.....	1023
<i>Karimova Gulchehra</i>	
Ta'lim boshqaruvida "yumshoq kuch" (soft skills): rahbar ayollarning psixologik va pedagogik mahorati...	1026
<i>Nomozova Roziya Omonovna</i>	
Ta'lim jarayonida psixologik muhitning ahamiyati.....	1029
<i>Qarshiboyeva Dilfuza Burliyevna</i>	
Boshlang'ich ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellektdan foydalanishning samaradorligi.....	1033
<i>Qo'chqorov Mirzavali</i>	
Tarbiyachi va bola o'rtasidagi muloqotning psixologik ahamiyati.....	1036
<i>Qodirova Malikaxon Kaxramonovna</i>	
Umumta'lim tizimida o'qituvchilarning sifat faoliyatini baholovchi tizim yaratish.....	1040
<i>Sharipova Umeda Tolibjonovna</i>	
Maktabgacha yoshdagi nutq nuqsonli bolalarda kommunikativ kompetensiyani rivojlantirishda zamonaviy logopedik va multimodal ta'lim texnologiyalarining samaradorligi.....	1045
<i>Hasanova Gulnoz Qosimovna, Jo'rayeva Gulibonu G'ayrat qizi</i>	
Musiqqa o'qituvchilarida ijrochilik mahoratini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik xususiyatlari.....	1050
<i>Azimjonova Gulxayoxon Shuxratjon qizi</i>	
Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni ijtimoiy-pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlash pedagogik muammo sifatida.....	1053
<i>Shanazarov Otabek</i>	
Tarbiya fanida milliy-ma'naviy meros va hadislar asosida shaxsning ma'naviy-axloqiy kamolotini shakllantirishning ilmiy-pedagogik paradigmalari.....	1058
<i>Axmedov Boburjon Vasikovich</i>	
Pedagoglar malakasini oshirish samaradorligini baholash mezonlari.....	1063
<i>Muminova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna</i>	
Современная детская литература: тенденции, проблемы и воспитательный потенциал.....	1067
<i>Дустова Дилдора Собиржановна</i>	
Complex Variants of Congenital Cleft Palate: Surgical Attacks.....	1070
<i>Anvarova Muhtasar Anvarovna</i>	

COMPLEX VARIANTS OF CONGENITAL CLEFT PALATE: SURGICAL ATTACKS

Anvarova Muhtasar Anvarovna

Samarkand state medical university, Samarkand, Uzbekistan

ORCID: 0009-0002-5146-7164

Abstract: The scientific rationale and clinical application of surgical techniques for the correction of congenital clefts of the upper lip and palate are extensively documented in specialized literature, demonstrating the diversity of maxillofacial abnormalities [7, 13, 20, 21, 23–25]. Global and domestic experience, together with accumulated research findings, drive the development and implementation of innovative approaches to the correction of craniofacial deformities. This contributes to the continuous improvement of surgical and rehabilitative techniques, the integration of advanced technologies into pediatric healthcare systems, and the advancement of specialized medical expertise [1, 4, 17, 19, 20, 23, 24].

Key words: congenital cleft palate, uranoplasty, palatoplasty, maxillofacial surgery, pediatric surgery.

Annotatsiya: Yuqori lab va tanglayning tug'ma yoriqlarini jarrohlik yo'li bilan tuzatish usullarining ilmiy asoslari va klinik qo'llanilishi maxsus adabiyotlarda keng yoritilgan bo'lib, bu maksillofasial anomaliyalar xilma-xilligini namoyon etadi [7, 13, 20, 21, 23–25]. Jahon va milliy tajriba, shuningdek, ilmiy tadqiqotlar natijalari yuz-jag' deformatsiyalarini tuzatishning innovatsion usullarini ishlab chiqish va joriy etishga turtki bo'lmoqda. Bu esa jarrohlik va reabilitatsiya usullarining uzluksiz takomillashuviga, pediatrik sog'liqni saqlash tizimiga zamonaviy texnologiyalarning joriy etilishiga hamda ixtisoslashgan tibbiy bilimlarning rivojlanishiga olib keladi [1, 4, 17, 19, 20, 23, 24].

Kalit so'zlar: tug'ma tanglay yorig'i, uranoplastika, palatoplastika, maksillofasial jarrohlik, bolalar jarrohligi.

Аннотация: Научное обоснование и клиническое применение хирургических методов коррекции врождённых расщелин верхней губы и нёба широко освещены в специализированной литературе, что отражает разнообразие челюстно-лицевых аномалий [7, 13, 20, 21, 23–25]. Мировой и отечественный опыт, а также результаты научных исследований способствуют разработке и внедрению инновационных методов коррекции челюстно-лицевых деформаций. Это, в свою очередь, приводит к постоянному совершенствованию хирургических и реабилитационных технологий, внедрению современных технологий в систему педиатрического здравоохранения и развитию специализированных медицинских знаний [1, 4, 17, 19, 20, 23, 24].

Ключевые слова: врождённая расщелина нёба, уранопластика, палатопластика, челюстно-лицевая хирургия, детская хирургия.

INTRODUCTION

Established “classical” technologies are frequently being refined and further elaborated, often with the incorporation of additional materials or implants (such as plastics and bioinert metals). These materials are surgically introduced into damaged structures of the maxillofacial region, meet safety standards, remain biologically inert relative to surrounding tissues, and promote guided regeneration while providing sufficient support for maxillary restoration [5, 6, 8, 9, 15].

It is important to emphasize that, in most cases, the application of advanced surgical techniques for cheilorrhinoplasty and uranoplasty requires a comprehensive set of therapeutic and rehabilitation measures involving highly qualified multidisciplinary specialists. Nevertheless, the core phase of this treatment protocol remains the surgical intervention itself [7, 11, 13, 14, 16, 18, 21]. Contemporary research also indicates that surgical approaches to correcting congenital cleft lip and palate continue to improve: multi-stage procedures are being gradually abandoned, enabling correction of maxillofacial structures by the age of 2-3 years [2, 3, 7, 11].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Surgical correction of congenital cleft palate has evolved from simple anatomical closure to functional reconstruction aimed at ensuring proper speech development and preservation of midfacial growth. Traditional “classical” techniques, such as the Langenbeck bipediced flap and the Veau-Wardill-Kilner pushback uranoplasty, established the foundation for modern cleft surgery [7, 13, 20]. However, contemporary studies indicate that pushback techniques often resulted in extensive areas of denuded bone, leading to subsequent maxillary growth retardation and severe orthodontic complications.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

An analysis of medical records from 2022-2025 at Dental Clinic No. 1 in Samarkand showed that children underwent primary surgical intervention for congenital cleft palate. Among 109 examined cases, 53 children (aged 1 year to 8 years and 2 months) presented with complex cleft palate variants characterized by asymmetry of the soft palate and uvula, along with a deficiency of native tissues. The study utilized statistical and clinical research methods, structural analysis, and photographic assessment of patients.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Consultations for correction of complex cleft palate were most frequently observed in children aged 2-4 years, with isolated cases occurring between 5-8 years. Delayed presentation was associated with remote residence, lack of local specialists, adverse social conditions of parents, or placement of the child in specialized institutions following abandonment at birth. A proprietary classification system was applied to all 53 patients with complex cleft palate types to improve diagnostic precision and optimize the selection of surgical techniques for correcting tissue asymmetry [10, 12]. Evaluation of cleft morphology, optimal age for uranoplasty, level of orthodontic preparation, and surgical approaches enabled prediction of healing duration and determination of subsequent stages of multidisciplinary rehabilitation at Dental Clinic No. 1 in Samarkand.

In certain cases, congenital asymmetrical cleft palate presented with severe features, including diastasis between palatal fragments exceeding 1.5-2 cm with significant tissue deficiency, as well as diastasis in the alveolar process region exceeding 0.5-0.6 cm. These conditions required a modified surgical strategy involving the use of “titanium silk,” regardless of patient age. This material is widely applied in various medical fields, including general surgery, dentistry, gynecology, and cosmetology. “Titanium silk” consists of 99.9% titanium and demonstrates high biochemical and biomechanical compatibility, supports guided soft tissue regeneration, and exhibits resistance to microbial colonization due to its non-absorptive properties (it does not absorb blood, saliva, or tissue fluids). Its fine-mesh structure prevents communication between the oral and nasal cavities even in cases of mucoperiosteal suture dehiscence [2, 5, 6, 8, 15].

Uranoplasty for complex cleft palate using “titanium silk” includes the following stages: incision–refreshing the cleft margins under endotracheal anesthesia, with incision type determined by cleft morphology (isolated cleft: triangular flap with base at the alveolar process; unilateral complete cleft: turnover flap from the larger maxillary segment; bilateral complete cleft: quadrangular turnover flap from the intermaxillary bone region); preparation of soft palate margins by excising 0.3-0.5 cm of oral mucosa to allow tension-free nasal mucosa suturing; Langenbeck incisions extending posterior to the alveolar processes; elevation of mucoperiosteal flaps with preservation of neurovascular bundles; detachment and repositioning of soft palate muscles from the posterior margin of the horizontal palatine plate; correction of asymmetry using the Rogozhina method (2019) [12], involving transverse incisions of the nasal mucosa on the shortened side to equalize length; implantation of “titanium silk” in cases of significant tissue deficiency according to defect configuration; transverse suturing of repositioned muscles; closure of oral mucosa with absorbable sutures; and postoperative placement of an iodoform tampon under a protective plate, removed on the second postoperative day.

Clinical examples: Case 1–Patient M., aged 1 year and 3 months, diagnosed with congenital partial cleft palate with asymmetry of the soft palate and uvula; cleft width at “Line A” was 1.0 cm, with the right uvula shortened by 0.9 cm. Outcome: successful sparing uranoplasty using the author’s method. Case 2–Patient A., aged 1 year and 4 months, diagnosed with congenital bilateral complete cleft palate with asymmetry and tissue deficiency; cleft width was 1.9 cm at “Line A” and 2.2 cm at the soft palate. Outcome: successful uranoplasty with preservation of anatomical structures using “titanium silk.” In all 53 cases, healing occurred by primary intention, normal feeding function was restored, and no oronasal communication was observed. Prolonged healing exceeding three months was noted in only two cases with defects larger than 2.0 cm.

CONCLUSION

Selection of optimal surgical management for complex cleft palate should be individualized and based on a multidisciplinary approach. The use of “titanium silk” as an adjunct material for wide clefts (greater than 1.5-2 cm) ensures reliable defect closure at any age and facilitates effective comprehensive rehabilitation. This multimodal approach is recommended for implementation in specialized clinical settings with appropriate expertise.

References:

1. Mitropanova MN. Features of the functioning of the immune system in children with congenital cleft lip and palate at the stages of surgical treatment. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2017;16(61):79-83. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=29206060>
2. Nesterova IV, Mitropanova MN, Chudilova GA, Lomtadze LV, Gaivoronskaya TV. Effect of imbalance of regulatory cytokines and osteocalcin on osteogenesis in children with congenital cleft lip and palate in postnatal ontogenesis. *Dentistry*. 2020;99(1):77-81. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42479509>
3. Rogova LN, Fomenko IV, Timoshenko AN. Immunological and microbiological characteristics of the oral mucosa in children with congenital cleft lip and palate (literature review). *Volgograd Scientific Medical Journal*. 2016;3(51):19-22. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=27249177>
4. Khripach LV, Knyazeva TD, Zheleznyak EV, Makovetskaya AK, Koganova ZI, Budarina OV, Lebedeva NV, Ingel FI, Demina NN. Adaptive changes in biochemical and immunological parameters of mixed saliva under the influence of atmospheric air pollution on preschool children. *International Journal of Applied and Basic Research*. 2019;6:68-73. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=38489006>
5. Kovalevsky AM, Kovalevsky VA. Etiology and pathogenesis of inflammatory periodontal diseases (literature review). Part 1. *Institute of Dentistry*. 2017;4:88-90. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=32302028>
6. Dovbnaya ZhA, Golovskaya GG, Galkina OP, Ter-pogosyan DA, Ablaev KD, Ablaev KD. Changes in the factors of non-specific protection of the oral cavity in children with gingivitis against the background of the use of essential oils and bentonite clay. *Bulletin of Modern Clinical Medicine*. 2021;14(6):33-37. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=47463336>
7. Osokina AS, Maslak EE, Yakovlev AT. The level of immunoglobulin A in saliva depending on the presence and severity of early childhood caries. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2020;20(4):304-309. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44583346>
8. Danilova MA, Aleksandrova LI. Quality of life in children with congenital cleft lip and palate. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2018;17(3):54-57. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=36347137>
9. Shevchenko OL, Antonova AA. The composition of mixed saliva and indicators of caries in deciduous teeth and its complications in children. *Endodontics Today*. 2015;4:8-11. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=25411139>
10. Kuriakose S, Sundaresan C, Mathai V, et al. A comparative study of salivary buffering capacity, flow rate, resting pH, and salivary immunoglobulin A in children with rampant caries and caries-resistant children. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent*. 2013;31(2):69-73. doi: 10.4103/0970-4388.115697
11. Skripkina GI. Clinical and laboratory parameters of the subclinical course of the carious process in childhood. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2017;16(4):24-27. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=32389346>
12. Musakhodzhaeva DA, Inoyatov AS, Yakubov SH. Some indicators of the immune system of children with congenital cleft lip and palate. *Problems of Biology and Medicine*. 2011;4(67):33. (In Russ.)
13. Agayeva NA. The role of secretory IgA in the pathology of the maxillofacial region. *Basic Research*. 2010;4:11-16. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=15107695>
14. Kaur A, Kwatra KS, Kamboj P. Evaluation of nonmicrobial salivary caries activity parameters and salivary biochemical indicators in predicting dental caries. *J Indian Soc Pedod Prev Dent*. 2012;30(3):212-217. doi: 10.4103/0970-4388.105013
15. Kubala E, Strzelecka P, Grzegocka M, et al. A review of selected studies that determine the physical and chemical properties of saliva in the field of dental treatment. *BioMed Research International*. 2018;ID6572381:13. doi: 10.1155/2018/6572381
16. Hemadi AS, Huang R, Zhou Y, Zou J. Salivary proteins and microbiota as biomarkers for early childhood caries risk assessment. *Int J Oral Sci*. 2017;9(11):e1. doi: 10.1038/ijos.2017.35
17. Al Amoudi N, Al Shukairy H, Hanno A. A comparative study of the secretory IgA immunoglobulins (s.IgA) in mothers and children with SECC versus a caries-free group children and their mothers. *J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2007;32(1):53-56. doi: 10.17796/jcpd.32.1.i338366jw54634q5
18. Lo Giudice G, Nicita F, Miliati A, et al. Correlation of s-IgA and IL-6 salivary with caries disease and oral hygiene parameters in children. *Dent J (Basel)*. 2019;8(1):3. doi: 10.3390/dj8010003
19. Parisotto TM, King WF, Duque C, et al. Immunological and microbiologic changes during caries development in young children. *Caries Res*. 2011;45(4):377-385. doi: 10.1159/000330230
20. Dovbnaya ZhA, Kolesnik KA, Golovskaya GG. Protective reactions of the oral cavity in children with chronic catarrhal gingivitis and its treatment. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2017;16(2):24-26. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=29206046>

21. Pukhova OS, Chernenko SV. Features of the dental status of children with congenital cleft lip and palate in permanent occlusion. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2004;3(3-4):34-36. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=9284441>
22. Yatskevich EE, Osokina GG. Chronic gingivitis in children with hereditary and congenital somatic pathology. *Dentistry for Everyone*. 2007;1:4-7. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=12516681>
23. Chuikin SV, Akat'eva GG, Chuikin OS, Grin' EA, Kuchuk KN. Dental morbidity in children with congenital cleft lip and palate in a region with ecotoxicants. *Dentistry of Childhood and Prevention*. 2019;19(4):15-19. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=42490586>
24. Chuikin OS, Davletshin NA, Chuikin SV, Akat'eva GG, Kuchuk KN, Ganieva RA, Muratov AM. State of periodontal tissues in children with congenital cleft palate and defect after uranoplasty. *Actual Problems in Dentistry*. 2021;17(4):105-112. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=47871063>
25. Chopra A, Laxhanpal M, Rao NC, Gupta N, Vashisth S. Oral health in 4-6 years children with cleft lip/palate: a case-control study. *N Am J Med Sci*. 2014;6(6):266-269. doi: 10.4103/1947-2714.134371
26. Stelzle F, Rohde M, Oetter N, Krug K, Riemann M, Adler W. Gingival esthetics and oral health-related quality of life in patients with cleft lip and palate. *Int J Oral Maxillofacial Surgery*. 2017;46(8):993-997. doi: 10.1016/j.ijom.2017.03.020
27. Funahashi K, Shiba T, Watanabe T, Nakagawa I, Moriyama K. Functional dysbiosis within dental plaque microbiota in cleft lip and palate patients. *Progress in Orthodontics*. 2019;20(1):11. doi: 10.1186/s40510-019-0265-1
28. Malay KK, Ravindran V, Kumar J. Gingival health status in children with and without cleft lip and palate: a case-control study. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*. 2020;14(4):5997-6003
29. Genco RJ, Borgnakke WS. Risk factors for periodontal disease. *Periodontol 2000*. 2013;62:59-94. doi: 10.1111/j.1600-0757.2012.00457.x
30. Brill EA, Zubareva EV, Yakimov KYu, Chizhov YuV, Galonsky VG. Experience in the treatment of chronic gingivitis in adolescents with dental anomalies and deformities. *Institute of Dentistry*. 2021;4(93):86-87. (In Russ.). Available at: <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=47486941>

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

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